

DIGITAL ECONOMY AND DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL ECONOMY IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Abstract: *The article talks about the practical importance, aspects, and foreign experience of the digital economy. In the conditions of today's rapidly developing global economy, the digital economy is in the initial stage of its development, and first of all, it is highlighted that it can significantly increase people's living standards, and this is its main benefit.*

Key words: *digital economy, digital technologies, development, system, Internet economy, international competition, digital technology, competition, communication.*

INTRODUCTION

The digital revolution, which is manifested as a new stage of economic and technological development, has rapidly changed human life, created wide opportunities, and started a period of further tightening of the international competition field.

Nowadays, the concept of digital economy has appeared in the economic theory and practice of a number of countries. It was characterized by the rapid development of digital technologies, the revolution in the information sector, and the acceleration of the globalization of the economy. The efficiency of their use has been translated into increasing knowledge, and socio-economic relations are expanding more and more.

The digital economy is used to represent two different concepts. First, the digital economy is considered a modern stage of development, characterized by the priority of creative work and information benefits. Secondly, the digital economy

is a unique concept, the object of its study is the information society. In the conditions of today's rapidly developing global economy, the digital economy is in the early stages of its development, and the complete transition to the digital information stage of our time is only a few years away.

As stated by the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "In order to achieve development, it is necessary and necessary for us to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies. This gives us the opportunity to follow the shortest path to progress. "

The digital economy is an economic activity in which the main factor in production and service is information in the form of numbers, with the help of processing a large amount of information and analyzing the result of this processing. is to implement more effective solutions than the previous system in production, service, technologies, devices, storage, product delivery. In other words, the digital economy is an activity connected with the development of digital computer technologies in the provision of online services, electronic payments, internet trade, crowdfunding and other types of industries. E-commerce, internet banking, electronic payments, internet advertising and, at the same time, internet games are seen as the main elements of digital economy development .

The main source of the digital segment of the economy is the growth of the transactional sector. In developed countries, this indicator makes up more than 70 percent of the Gross Domestic Product and combines public administration, consulting and information services, finance, wholesale and retail trade, as well as services (utility, personal and social).

The higher the diversification and dynamics of the economy, the greater the circulation of unique information within and outside the country, and the greater the information traffic within national economies. Therefore, the digital economy develops rapidly in markets where the number of participants is large and IT services are widespread. Undoubtedly, the effectiveness of the digital economy is

influenced not only by the coverage of information technologies and the availability of infrastructure, but also by standard economic criteria such as the business environment, human capital, and successful management instruments. Therefore, economic development relies on them, which means that these criteria are as important as before in the development of the digital economy. It is noted that digital technologies will dramatically change more than 50 percent of economy-related sectors. This vision is based on the fact that information technologies and digital platforms will dramatically change business models, eliminate intermediaries and optimize processes for their efficiency.

As a result of the study of the world experience, it became clear that in countries with a developed digital economy, the state (government) determines the rules of the market "game" in the digital economy for all participants of the game, and in this, the most important task of the state is for the participants of the game. creation of different, equal rights and opportunity conditions. That is, whether it is a large company or a small business in the market, they are equal. They are given the same opportunities. It ensures that government regulations are followed and that, ultimately, the average consumer receives a quality, up-to-date service or product. Therefore, for the development of the digital economy, the state should create equal conditions for everyone, market rules, laws, and contracts should be transparent as much as possible, and laws should be based on market demand (that is, it should be able to determine development trends in the market in advance and adopt the necessary regulatory documents). it is necessary to provide freedom for the participants of the game. Digital economy is developing in Uzbekistan as well as in other countries of the world. After the application of information technologies in our daily life, many opportunities are created for ordinary people. Nowadays , we can order many food products and meals without leaving home and have them delivered to our home.

The most active driver of the digital economy is the state. He is the main customer and consumer of the digital economy. For example, China spent around 9 billion dollars for these purposes . Internet resource Alibaba , which has a market capitalization of more than 210 billion dollars, proved that these investments were well directed. In particular, Japan has missed out on leading positions in the digital economy due to the fact that it has bought technology , but it has not been able to create its own productive networks in this direction and to maintain a consistently high level of technical development. South Korea, on the other hand, invests 1% of the national budget in e-government and e-intermediation (for e-commerce activities and public tender purchases), generating 10-15 billion dollars annually and receiving revenues that cover costs 30-40 times . In particular, this result was achieved by organizing call centers in the public and private sectors, creating mobile applications and reengineering state-owned internet platforms. Training of personnel working with information systems in public administration remains one of the important areas of this field . For example, in the 70s of the last century, in Belgium , special mobile groups of specialists (including teachers and students from specialized educational institutions) were organized to train employees of state bodies and configure systems directly for them at their workplaces. . Because the digital economy covers the whole world, any government project related to informatization and digitization should be studied comprehensively and based on a single coding system, identifying economic and management related information.

The digital economy is the main driver of corruption and the "black economy". Because numbers seal everything, store it in memory, provide information quickly when needed. In such conditions, it is impossible to hide any information, make secret deals, not to provide full information about this or that activity, the computer will reveal everything. The abundance and systematicity of information does not allow for lies and fraudulent activities, because it is impossible to cheat the system. As a result, it will not be possible to launder "dirty

money", steal funds, spend ineffectively and aimlessly, increase or hide them. This will increase the flow of legal funds into the economy, taxes will be paid on time and correctly, budget allocation will be open, funds directed to the social sphere will not be stolen, schools, hospitals, the money allocated for the roads will reach in full, etc.

The choice of the state to develop the digital economy opens up new directions in the field of information technologies and in general, in the field of electronic document circulation. The turn towards "digital technologies" was caused by the worldwide Internet network and the development of quality communication. It should be noted that today users of this system actively use Telegram bots to order food, various perfumes and modern clothing products. Also, various online stores and electronic payment systems are actively developing. So, our citizens believe in electronic transactions. Until now, users have been making small transactions that do not require large costs, and are not very willing to increase the average purchase volume. Now the issue is the development of medium and large economic transactions and financial transactions through digital technologies.

International experience shows that today digital technologies are rapidly developing mainly in the scientific community and the private sector. Therefore, the state should create a favorable ecosystem by supporting innovative projects and IT companies in these areas.

CONCLUSION

In short, the term "Digital" refers to the active use of information technology in all areas. If in the ordinary economy material goods are considered the main resource, in the digital economy it will be processed and transmitted information - data. After their analysis, a proper management solution is developed.

Also, the state should support modern methods of digital education in the field of supporting the innovative and digital ecosystem, develop norms for

effective regulation of innovative services, help in the development of new markets, and reduce risks arising from the deepening of technological processes. it is appropriate to take measures.

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